

Enhancing the Speaking Skills of Professionals Through Role Plays

S Archana

Assistant Professor, Department of English,
Anurag University, Venkatapur, Ghatkesar,
Medchal District, Hyderabad, Telangana, India - 500088

Abstract:

In the current professional world, communication is the key to success (plays a predominant role), and as a professional student, one needs to enhance effective speaking skills to compete in the workplace. In the process of transmitting the information, there is a need for professional students to develop speaking skills to express their ideas or the information. Role-playing is one of the best methods for improving the speaking abilities of students through different situations in different contexts, where their communicative competence can be enhanced, leading to better communicators. It also benefits the students thinking and understanding from a broader perspective before they participate and put forth their ideas. It also leads to multi-skill development, through which he develops persuasive, collaborative, interpersonal, and management skills. This paper tries to focus on the professional students speaking competence through role-plays, which make them face common and unusual situations, which enables them to gain self-confidence by using the language effectively in various situations and improving their contextual vocabulary.

Keywords: Professional World – Communicative Competence – Contextual Vocabulary

Introduction

In today's world, communication plays a major role in transmitting information in English from one part of the world to another. In the process of effective communication, enhancing speaking skills becomes a challenge for professional students as it becomes a major skill in passing information. In the process of speaking, students try to communicate their ideas, information, feelings, and opinions through words. In turn, they acquire language skills, which do not mean knowing the structure or the contextual vocabulary but knowing how to use the language for communication in transmitting information from one person to another person as to how we speak and make people understand the content. Students are involved in many activities as a part of their academic curriculum, whose main outcome is to improve their oral communication skills. Students, when involved in various activities, learn and acquire different perspectives on

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language skills, which become the course objective. In the process of enhancing better speaking skills, many activities are designed, and one among them is role play, through which students get an opportunity and exposure to improve their professional skills to meet the needs of the industry.

Role-Play and its Importance

Role-playing is one of the communicative teaching methods that is designed to develop the learners' speaking abilities and help them acquire language efficiency in different contexts. They also help them overcome glossophobia by involving them and participating in various situations. Students are also encouraged to experience various situations by being spontaneously involved in speaking activities to improve vocabulary. The main aspect of introducing role plays is to build students' verbal skills by emphasizing the processes involved in communication. They also help to develop language fluency by involving the students in classroom activities with enthusiasm. Through different role plays, students come across different situations where they are involved in thinking critically according to the context and acting spontaneously, which improves their confidence by improving their oral communication skills. They also encourage students to work collectively, leading to collaborative learning and helping them develop teamwork skills.

Benefits of Role Play Activities in Improving the Speaking Skills of Professional Students

- It provides a good platform for the students to experience different social contexts.
- As students are involved in spontaneous activities, they overcome stage fright and nervousness.
- Students, through different situations, can develop their contextual vocabulary.
- Develops critical thinking abilities as they are exposed to different situations.

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- It helps students overcome anxiety as they are continuously involved in classroom activities.
- Students can also overcome their shyness with constant participation.
- It makes students interact in a variety of circumstances.
- These activities help students improve their language fluency.
- Role-playing helps students improve their speaking skills in any social situation based on the appropriate feedback and suggestions given by the teachers.
- Students are provided with opportunities while participating in the activities to assess
- Develops competitive spirit among the students while participating in classroom activities.
- Role plays are put forth before the students to experience the real-world scenarios by placing themselves in the situations and coming up with new solutions.
- Develops critical observation of peers by improving their language fluency.

Conclusion

Role plays help students improve their intensification of understanding the real-life illustrations. It improves the student's development, especially in social contexts. With continuous practice, it provides the students with a platform where they can improve their language fluency, which leads to effective communication. Students were also able to improve other aspects such as pronunciation, enunciation, accuracy, vocabulary, and accuracy for acquiring better speaking skills. The facilities provided as a part of classroom activities were considered to be very beneficial for building the effective communication skills of the professional students to meet the needs of the industry.

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